

PRAGMATIC AWARENESS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH: A FOCUS ON SPEECH ACTS

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"Language is not simply a tool for communication; it is also a social marker. We use language to signal our identity, our social group, and our social status." - Deborah Tannen, communication expert and author.

ABSTRACT

While grammatical accuracy and vocabulary are essential components of language proficiency, they are insufficient for true communicative fluency. Sociocultural competence, which encompasses the ability to understand and navigate the sociolinguistic norms of a target language, is increasingly recognized as a key factor in successful language learning (Byram, 1997; Deardorff, 2006). However, measuring sociocultural competence remains a complex challenge. The field of pragmatics, the study of language in context, has become increasingly important in language teaching. It recognizes the crucial role that social factors, cultural norms, and contextual cues play in successful communication. This article delves into the teaching and learning of pragmatics, focusing on the concept of speech acts and their implications for language learners.

Key words: *Sociocultural Competence, Pragmatics, Intercultural Communication, Speech acts*

While mastering grammar and vocabulary is crucial for language acquisition, achieving fluency and effective communication requires more than just memorizing rules. Given the dominance of the communicative approach in language teaching, we assume that grammar explanations and grammar exercises will be well contextualized and discourse-based (Celce-Murcia and Olshtain 2000). That means we should show how grammar works in real situations, not just give rules. We also need to look at how native speakers actually use the language, not just guess how it works. To figure out how native speakers use grammar, we need to look at real examples of language they use and see how it fits into the whole conversation. This is a lot different from just looking at a few sentences and trying to understand the rules. Language teachers as well as scholars and researchers in the field of applied linguistics have been appealing the necessity to incorporate cultural knowledge into second and foreign

language teaching. (e.g., Lafayette, 1988; Moorjani & Field, 1988). Often times the crucial focus of second and foreign language teaching has been directed towards dispensing the rules of grammar and increasing the knowledge of vocabulary in the target language so that one can produce correct utterances in order to communicate. That is to say, competency in linguistic knowledge does not guarantee successful use of the language. In order to accomplish fruitful communication learners, need to be acquainted “Cultural competency”. Sometimes a key element often overlooked is the understanding and application of pragmatic norms – the unspoken rules and conventions of language use in a specific culture. Think of it this way: imagine learning a language solely from textbooks. You might be able to string together grammatically correct sentences, but would you know how to politely decline an invitation, offer a sincere compliment, or negotiate a price in a foreign market? This is where pragmatics comes in. The norms, which can significantly vary from one language to another, encompass aspects like politeness, directness, humor, and even the use of non-verbal cues. For instance, what might be considered polite in one culture could be perceived as overly formal or even rude in another. Learning and adapting to these subtle nuances allows individuals to navigate social situations effectively, build rapport, and ultimately achieve truly successful communication in the target language. It’s not just about speaking correctly; it’s about speaking appropriately and effectively within the cultural context. Hence, teaching English as a second language should prioritize the development of pragmatic competence, a task that presents unique challenges.

Pragmatics is the way we convey the meaning through the communication. The meaning includes verbal and non-verbal elements and it varies according to the context, to the relationship between utterers, also to many other social factors. Its dynamic growth makes English an international language that connects people all around the world. As a consequence, English can be regarded as the common focus of all English speakers who do not share a language or a culture. As a matter of fact, English is spoken in different settings and levels of intercommunication. As a result, speakers must know many pragmatic elements in order to avoid inaccuracies and misunderstandings during communication. Such a great usage of English language requires a pragmatic competence which will help all those who speak or learn English as a second language. Thomas defined pragmatic competence as “... the ability to analyze language in a conscious manner.” (as cited in Holmes & Brown, 2007, p 524). Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to comprehend, construct utterances which are accurate and appropriate to the social and cultural circumstances where the communication occurs. Being good at communicating means knowing how to use language well in different situations. Pragmatics is a valuable tool for understanding

the challenges faced by English learners and it helps us see how learners navigate the complexities of English. This competence should be a leading goal for all those who teach English as a second language, which simultaneously represents a challenging task as well.

Imagine a student who flawlessly combines verbs but struggles to understand the nuances of a casual conversation, a business meeting, or a formal presentation. This is where pragmatics steps in. It's about understanding cultural differences, social cues and content. Without this understanding, learners may be fluent but lack the confidence and social skills to navigate real-world interactions effectively. Low level of understanding of pragmatic norms of speech acts could lead to wrong production of spoken discourse (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain.2000)

It is essential that all teachers of English as a second language prioritize developing pragmatic norms of speech acts in their students by making it real with different real life scenarios, role- playing, case studies. Understanding the intended meaning, rather than just the literal words, is crucial because some sentences carry hidden meanings, convey more than what they literally say. Pragmatics helps us understand that words can carry different meanings depending on context, tone, and even body language. What sounds polite in one culture might be considered rude in another. Learners should be aware of about intended function of language. For instance, "Can you open the window?" is a polite request, not a question about ability. It is also vital to teach functions explicitly during lessons like requesting, complaining, apologizing, disagreeing, and complimenting. Written-scenarios is also beneficial activity to raise students' pragmatic awareness where leaners can analyze and respond to written scenarios involving complaints, demonstrating their understanding of appropriate communication strategies. Language corpora is another measurement tool which can provide insights into how native speakers handle different speech acts by using various authentic materials like conversations, online forums.

CONCLUSION

Developing a comprehensive measure of sociocultural competence requires a multi-dimensional approach, taking into account linguistic features, politeness strategies, cultural appropriateness, and negotiation skills. Teaching and learning pragmatics, particularly speech acts, is essential for developing communicative competence in language learners. By incorporating explicit instruction, awareness-raising activities, interactive exercises, and authentic materials, educators can equip learners with the tools necessary to navigate the complexities of language use in different contexts. By incorporating these strategies into the lessons, teachers

empower learners to go beyond grammar and master the art of communicative competence, enabling them to confidently navigate the world of English in all its diverse and dynamic forms.

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